

Female Representation in Advertisements: A Critical Discourse Analysis

FAREEHA AAZAM

Lecturer, Department of English
National College of Business Administration & Economics, Multan, Pakistan.
Email: fareeha.aazam786@gmail.com
Tel: +92-341-0689319

TANVEER BAIG

(Corresponding Author)
Assistant Professor, Department of English,
Bahauddin Zakariya University, Sub-Campus, Lodhran, Pakistan.
Email: tanveerbaig@bzu.edu.pk
Tel: +92 -333-6003095

AHMAD FARAZ

BS Scholar, Department of English
Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.
Email: ahmadfarazkotadu@gmail.com
Tel: +92- 332- 6433757

Abstract

This study focuses on the advertisements in TV from a Feministic point of view. This research mainly focuses on the use of language in TV advertisements and strategies used by the advertisers to influence their customers. The study shows how sexist language is used in advertisements and how female body is represented through language. For linguistic and semiotic analyses, Fairclough's (2001) critical discourse analysis and Machin's (2007) multimodal analysis have been used. The findings indicate that in advertisements different social and cultural contexts are used to present women. The advertisements promote a beautiful female body. This study further reveals that the ideology of beauty is constructed through language and different stereotypes related to female body are created through advertisements. So, the advertising language is used to control people's minds and create an idealized lifestyle.

Keywords: *Female representation, Advertisements, Sexist language, Critical Discourse Analysis, Multimodal Analysis, Ideology, Advertisers.*

Introduction

At present, there is a strict competition in advertisements; therefore advertisers use different techniques to attract their customers. They use female body with persuasive language to attract their customers. Different beauty product companies advertise their products through different mediums to influence people especially women. Television is one of the medium which is used quite effectively for this purpose. The producers make persuasive TV commercials because they reach a vast number of people easily. Due to the effectiveness of the medium almost all beauty products are advertised on television. These advertisements provide a lot of information about their product and influence the people. Celebrity endorsement is also used in advertisements to catch the people attention. These advertisements create a beautiful and imagery world through the flawless personality of the model. They convey the message to the audience that they can transform their looks by using the advertised products. All these commercials are made for monetary

benefits and therefore companies invest money in abundance to commercialize and sell their products. In this regard, they use every medium like radio, television, newspaper and magazines etc. the choice of medium for any product's advertisement depends upon lots of factors and age is one of the most important factors. Advertisements are made keeping in view the target group for whom the product is produced. For example, if their target group is young then they advertise products on internet as well as on television. These mediums are used tactfully to advertise the products as people can easily be influenced through attractive language and visuals.

According to Cook (2001) advertisements not only persuade their customers but also mould the opinions and thoughts of people. Advertisers not only sell their products but also change the society. People buy the advertised products which are not useful or necessary for them. He also believes advertisements give a lot of information about their product and also give warnings to people.

According to Baudrillard (2005) beauty product advertisements pressurize and influence the women to maintain their beauty and beauty becomes a complete religious imperative for them. An elegant image of women is stereotyped through these advertisements and for this purpose beautiful visuals and attractive language is used. According to Jhally (1995) advertising is the most influential institution of socialization in modern society. These advertisements also change the faith of women and they rely on beauty products to get the beautiful skin and body. Advertisements change the reality and mindset of the people and they buy these advertised products to make their life imagery as per shown in the advertisement. Advertisers control the people's mind and exercise their power through advertisements.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of this study:

- To study language critically in beauty product advertisements.
- To analyze visuals in these advertisements for identifying different types of discursive techniques used to change the beliefs of women.
- To study the discourses of advertisements generating stereotypical images of women beauty.

Research Questions

The study addresses the following research questions:

1. What linguistic and visual features are used to influence the people in beauty product advertisements?
2. Which types of discursive techniques are used to change the beliefs of women?

Literature Review

Lee (1992, p.8) states "Language is an instrument for the assignment of the phenomena of human experience to conceptual categories it is clearly not simply a mirror that reflects reality. Rather it functions to impose structure on our perceptions."

According to Fairclough (2001) critical discourse analysis studies the written, spoken, printed text and it also studies the signs, gestures and symbols in a given text. Critical discourse analysis explores and analyses the hidden issues in a text. As Coffin (2001) states that critical discourse analysis is very important to interpret text in a specific social and cultural context and it also studies the production and consumption of text. According to Lukes (1986) and Wrong (1979), power is practiced in groups and societies through discourse. Powerful people exercised power through language because they have privileged access to wealth and knowledge.

Price (1998, p. 38) states “an ideology is a specific example of organized belief.” Eagleton (1991) describes that ideology belonged to knowledge and it is a set of ideas or beliefs. People and groups follow specific ideologies in their daily life. Waterberg (1990) states power is practiced in a group or society through language. Gramsci (1971) further explains hegemony and power. He states that elite class people controls other people because they have authoritative roles in society.

Kumar (2004) states that advertisers influence and control the target group of people and promote their products by using different activities and also give the information. According to Arens (2002) people expect advertisers to be proud of their products and probably do not mind if they puff them a little. But when advertisers cross the line between simply giving their point of view and creating false expectations, that is when people began to object. According to Chauhan (2006) advertisements persuade and attract the people and they buy the advertised products. Through attractive and persuasive language advertisers promote their product and create a stereotypical idealized image of beauty. Mills (2003, p. 46) describes that “in critical discourse analysis, it is assumed that context consists of background assumptions, shared conventions, and also variables such as gender, race, class, ethnicity, and so on.”

Machin (2007) describes two types of semiotic representations that are denotation and connotation. In denotation, images that describe an event or indicate some places or different things. While in connotation, a specific image explains a concept or describes a specific thing. Following are the four connotation barriers: Poses, Settings, Objects and Photogenia.

According to Barthes (1977) people share different symbols and icons like words in their communication which explain a concept or idea. As Price (1998) states that semiology is the study about sign system and its meaning in language. A specific meaning is conveyed through the sign used in language. Hodge and Kress (1988) describe semiotic system as social semiotic system and it is belonged to multimodality. And through this system power and social relations are allowed in a society.

Chandler (2007, p. 1-2) “semiotics is the study of signs and it is not only the study of visual signs, but it includes words, sounds and body language.” According to Machin and Mayr (2012) there is no neutral language or visual. Behind every language and visual there is a hidden and revealed ideology or point of view. Media is using specific language and images to catch the attention of audience and they are portraying different things according to their ideologies and reshaping the people’s thoughts and concepts.

Research Methodology

Sample selected for this research paper are five television advertisements, all are beauty products. The purpose behind the selection of only beauty products is that beauty products are manufactured and marketed by keeping in view the strong desire of women to keep them attractive and young and thus they are presumed to use beauty product more as compared to men. These advertisements are also available on internet. We have selected the beauty products randomly. Following advertisements are selected as the sample of this study:

1. Olay regenerist cream,
2. L’Oreal color protect conditioner and shampoo,
3. Pantene shampoo,
4. New Dove face-wash
5. Garnier light fairness moisturizer

Theoretical Framework

The present study draws upon Fairclough (2001) critical discourse analysis approach and Machin (2007) multimodal analysis. In textual analysis vocabulary, grammar, cohesion and text structure is observed. In Discourse practice, production, distribution and consumption of text are evaluated. In social practice, it has been observed how discourse is used in different social, cultural and ideological situations. Discourses of advertisements are seen as a language and social processes and there is also a relationship between languages 'texts' and social practice.

Machin (2007) multimodal analysis is also used for visual analysis. Every picture connotes and denotes according to social context and there are hidden meanings behind a specific image and language. In visual analysis gaze of participants, color and poses are observed. Qualitative analysis is used for this research because it is most appropriate for this research. This study investigates how media discourse manipulates and construct the meaning of words in people's mind.

Data Collection

The data for the present study is collected from internet since commercials can be downloaded freely. The researchers randomly selected the sample from the beauty products of different nature ranging from facial creams to hair treatment. Advertisements on shampoo, beauty cream, face wash, moisturizer and hair color protector were downloaded and one advertisement from each was selected for the analysis. Framework of critical discourse analysis by Fairclough (2001) for linguistic analysis and for semiotic analysis Machin (2007) multimodal analysis is used. The three-dimensional framework contains micro level, meso level and macro level which explores the formation of discourse as a text and as discourse and social practice respectively. It also identifies the relationship between language, ideology and power. This study is focused on how the advertisers use persuasive linguistic features to attract their customers and how they change the people's attitudes through the advertisement content and create a stereotypical idealized image of beauty.

Data Analysis

The linguistic analysis is based on Fairclough's (2001) three-dimensional framework which deconstructs texts on three levels; micro level (textual analysis), meso level (discourse practice analysis) and macro level (social practice analysis). The semiotic analysis is based on Machin (2007) in which pose, color and gaze are observed.

Visual Analysis

For visual analysis Machin's (2007) multimodal analysis has been observed.

Visual Analysis of Figure 1: Olay Regenerist Cream

In this advertisement, a famous, celebrity Katie Holmes says that she is beautiful due to Olay regenerist cream. In this advertisement it is also shown that she is an awarded heroine due to Olay cream.

In the below picture, she is directly gazing towards the viewers which describe her confidence. It also seems that she is interacting directly and conveying a meaningful message. There is a smile on her face and her body is glowing which is the result of the continuous use of this beauty cream. It connotes that she is enjoying the moment as she looks gorgeous with the flawless skin. She is wearing black dress and there is also a black color in the background.

Figure 1: Olay Regenerist Cream

The use of black color in the background and in the foreground basically makes her look prominent and especially her glowing skin of the face and body shines through it. Red color is also used in this advertisement at the bottom where company's name is written. The contrast of red and black is meaning potential as both colors are bold and sharp and in this ad each is fulfilling the purpose of the advertiser. Sharp colors are basically used by the advertisers because they catch the viewer's attention. Here, both model and product are well fit in the frame to achieve the aim of the advertisers.

Visual Analysis of Figure 2: L'Oreal Color Protect Conditioner and Shampoo

Figure 2: L'Oreal Conditioner and Shampoo

In this advertisement a beautiful girl with long red hair is shown. The advertisement is about color protecting shampoo that protects the color of hair for 60 days. In this advertisement, model hairs are dyed and she is using L'OREAL shampoo to protect her hair color. In the above figure, heroine is gazing towards the viewers directly and her face is serious. She is conveying a message directly through her gaze and body posture. Red, White and black color combinations are used in this advertisement which are catching the attention of the viewers.

Visual Analysis of Figure 3: Pantene Shampoo

In this advertisement, a famous celebrity Selena Gomez says that before using the Pantene her hair break off but now her hair are strong and longer due to Pantene.

Figure 3: Pantene Shampoo

In the above figure, she is wearing a white sleeveless dress. Her body posture is relaxed and she puts her one hand on her back. She is also gazing towards the viewers directly. White, yellow and black colors are used in this advertisement. White color seems dominant than others because it conveys a softness and purity.

Visual Analysis of Figure 4: New Dove Face Wash

In this advertisement, a beautiful girl is using dove face wash her skin is bouncy and soft due to dove face wash. It is shown beautiful skin is only due to dove face wash.

Figure 4: Dove Face Wash

Model is also making direct interaction with viewers. Her skin is white and glowing and there is a smile on her face and she is wearing pink lipstick. White color is mostly used in this advertisement which describes beauty and purity.

Visual Analysis of Figure 5: Garnier Light Fairness Moisturizer

In this advertisement, a famous celebrity Priyanka Chopra says that her skin is spot free due to Garnier moisturizer. In this advertisement, it is shown that famous celebrity has a beautiful and spot free skin due to this product. Her gaze is towards the audience and it seems that she is conveying a message directly. There are mostly light colors are used like white, yellow and green color. Advertisers not only focus the beautiful face but also her body curves too. It is highlighted that by using this product a woman can get spot free skin. All linguistic captions are capital, bold and large font size that catches the attention of viewers.

Figure 5: Garnier Moisturizer

Linguistic Analysis

For linguistic analysis Fairclough's (2001) following three step model has been adapted.

Textual Analysis

Textual analysis discussed the attractive linguistic features such as vocabulary and syntax which influence the people to buy the product.

Use of Pronouns

In this study, first and second person is mostly used in advertisements to make the friendly relationship between presenter and viewer. Common pronouns such as 'you', 'your', 'I', 'my' and 'we' are used in beauty product advertisements. Advertisers address the viewer directly and personally because when people addressed directly and individually, it becomes highly valued. According to Fairclough (1989) it is called 'synthetic personalization'. Pronoun 'we' shows power and authority while 'you' indicates the direct and personal address to viewer. The use of 'we' and 'our' make the distinction between 'us' and 'them'. Examples of pronouns in beauty product advertisements are given below:

'I'll take beauty into my own hand'. [Olay Regenerist Cream]

'Make the color **you** love last with color vibrancy'. ['Oreal Color Protect Conditioner and Shampoo]

'So, **I** can love my hair longer.' [Pantene Shampoo]

'See what happens when **your** skin has a beautiful bounce'. [New Dove Face Wash]
'His spots, **I** love, but **my** spots, they just had to go'. [Garnier Light Fairness Moisturizer]

Persuasive Language

Advertisers use persuasive language to influence the viewers to buy their products. Imperatives are also used for this purpose. By using imperatives advertisers make a friendly and closer relationship with their viewer's. Following imperatives are used in beauty product advertisements:

'**Keep** sprite' [L 'Oreal Color Protect Conditioner and Shampoo]

'**Get** even faster results with Pantene expert our most intensely concentrated pro-v formula'. [Pantene Shampoo]

'**See** what happens when your skin has a beautiful bounce.' [New Dove Face Wash]

Disjunctive Syntax

Another strategy which is used in advertisements disjunctive syntax (sentences without subjects or verbs). There are following examples of disjunctive syntax in advertisements:

'Olay your best beautiful.' [Olay Regenerist Cream]

'L'Oreal color vibrancy.' [L 'Oreal Color Protect Conditioner and Shampoo]

'Pantene, strong is beautiful.' [Pantene Shampoo]

'Bouncy skin is happy skin.' [New Dove Face Wash]

'1, 2, 3 and spot free.' [Garnier Light Fairness Moisturizer]

Vocabulary

Vocabulary is used as a tool to make the ideologies. Adjectives are also used in the advertisements of beauty products. Positive adjectives describe the qualities of product while negative adjectives describe the problems before using the product. Following are the examples of negative and positive adjectives in advertisements:

Positive Adjectives

Regenerates, new, micro sculpting, stunningly, youthful, best, beautiful, my, unbreakable, micro, every, stronger, strong, beautiful, faster, most intensely, beautiful, extra, serum, bouncy, happy and pure lemon. Positive adjectives describe the positive qualities of product and it changes the ideologies of people. According to Cook (2001) it is a 'fusion' that causes the useless products with attractive qualities. Positive adjectives describe an idealized woman with certain qualities. These adjectives create emotions, desires, dreams and fantasy world in the mind of viewers.

Negative Adjectives

Drastic, weak and dark spots.

Sentence Structure

In advertisements, compound words are also used such as:

re-generates, youthful, antioxidant, grow-up, break-off, un-breakable, coming-back.

Present tense is used in the advertisements. All the sentences are declarative and simple. Future tense is also used for suggestions and advices. Most of the sentences in advertisements are active sentences. Passive voice is also used in some advertisements. Example of passive voice is given below:

'New skin is revealed in just 5 days without drastic measures.' [Olay Regenerist Cream]

Scientific and Technical Words

In advertisements, there are also scientific and technical words that attract the viewers. With these scientific words, advertisers show that their product is up to date with latest technology. These technical words also play an important role to attract the viewers to buy that product. The examples of scientific and technical words are given below:

‘Olay regenerist micro sculpting cream regenerates surface cells for stunningly youthful, award winning skin.’ [Olay Regenerist Cream]

‘The shampoo system with antioxidant [UV] seals in color vibrancy for the 60 days.’ [L ‘Oreal Color Protect Conditioner and Shampoo]

‘The new pro-v formula micro targets weak spots, making every inch stronger.’ [Pantene Shampoo]

‘Only new dove face wash has nutrium moisture beauty serum that nourishes skin from deep within.’ [New Dove Face Wash]

‘Garnier light fairness moisturizer, in which pure lemon essence sun cream.’ [Garnier Light Fairness Moisturizer]

Slogans

Advertisers also use the slogans in advertisements to catch the viewer attention and it is easy to remember products with specific slogans or taglines. There are following slogans of beauty product advertisements:

‘Olay your best beautiful.’ [Olay Regenerist Cream]

‘Expert care for the mending hair.’ [L ‘Oreal Color Protect Conditioner and Shampoo]

‘Pantene, strong is beautiful.’ [Pantene Shampoo]

‘New dove face wash makes skin bouncy with every wash.’ [New Dove Face Wash]

‘Take care Garnier.’ [Garnier Light Fairness Moisturizer]

Numbers are also used in advertisements. Examples are given below:

‘New skin is revealed in just **5** days without drastic measures.’ [Olay Regenerist Cream]

‘The shampoo system with antioxidant [UV] seals in color vibrancy for the **60** days’. [L ‘Oreal Color Protect Conditioner and Shampoo]

‘**1** lightening skin tone, **2** reduces dark spots, **3** sun cream prevents them coming back’. [Garnier Light Fairness Moisturizer]

In of all of these advertisements a beautiful and idealized female body is portrayed through language. The attractive and persuasive language is used to describe the female beauty which creates a false impression. These advertisements influence women to buy the beauty products for beautiful skin. They also mislead the people and change their behavior and attitude by creating a false image of beauty.

Discourse Practice Analysis

This level analyses how power relations are performed in production and distribution of text. In this level, advertisers use different techniques to influence their customers. Techniques and strategies used by the advertisers are described in following table 1.

Table 1: Discourse Strategies

Strategies used in advertisement	Linguistic devices
Invoking Deficiencies	without drastic measures [Olay Regenerist cream] strands always break off [Pantene Shampoo] reduces dark spots [Garnier Moisturiser]
Emotive words	stunningly youthful [Olay Regenerist cream], love [L’Oreal shampoo and conditioner], beautiful [Pantene] beautiful bounce [Dove face wash], Flowers glow [Garnier moisturiser]
Positive self-representation	Olay regenerist instantly changes the look of skin, regenerates surface cells. [Olay Regenerist Cream] L’Oreal Paris the no:1 brand for colour treated hair.[L O’Real Colour Vibrancy] Get even faster results with Pantene expert our most intensely concentrated pro v formula [Pantene Shampoo] New dove face wash gives skin an extra bounce. [Dove Face Wash] Garnier light fairness moisturiser, in which pure lemon essence sun cream. [Garnier Light Moisturiser]
Puffery words	The regenerist collection world no: 1 Olay your best beautiful. [Olay Regenerist cream] L’Oreal Paris the no:1 brand for colour treated hair .[L O’Real Shampoo and Conditioner] The new pro-v formula micro targets weak spots, making every inch stronger. [Pantene Shampoo] Only new dove face wash has nutrium moisture beauty serum that nourishes skin from deep within. [Dove Face Wash] It’s a cream that does so, 1, 2 and 3. 1 lightening skin tone, 2 reduces dark spots, 3 sun cream prevent them coming back. [Garnier Moisturiser]
Celebrity approval	Celebrity approval is also used in advertisement like Kattie Holmes in Olay cream, Selena Gomez in Pantene and Priyanka Chopra in Garnier moisturizer. “I’ll take beauty into my own hands” [Katie Holmes] But now Pantene is making my hair practically unbreakable [Selena Gomez] It’s a cream that does so. [Priyanka Chopra]
Manufacturing consent through Implication	Olay regenerist instantly changes the look of skin, regenerates surface cells. [Olay Regenerist Cream] The shampoo system with antioxidant [UV] seals in colour vibrancy for the 60 days. [L O’Real Conditioner and Shampoo] The new pro-v formula micro targets weak spots, making every inch stronger. [Pantene Shampoo] New dove face wash makes skin bouncy with every wash. [Dove Face Wash] Flowers glow in seven day survive. [Garnier Moisturiser]
Scientific evidence	Olay regenerist micro sculpting cream regenerates surface cells for stunningly youthful, award winning skin. [Olay Regenrist cream] The shampoo system with antioxidant [UV] seals in colour vibrancy for the 60 days. [L O’Real Shampoo and Conditioner] Get even faster results with Pantene expert our most intensely concentrated pro-v formula. [Pantene shampoo]

In beauty product advertisements, the main targets of advertisers are women. Advertisers change the beliefs of women by using persuasive language. According to Fill (2002) advertisers influence their customers and pressurize them to buy their product they do not use before. And they also influence women to care about their beauty with recommended products.

Advertisers also use the authoritative words like 'we' and it shows that they are different and unique than 'others'.

Advertisements create an idealized female image that has beautiful bouncy skin, long and beautiful hair and spot free skin. Celebrity endorsement is also used to convince the viewers. Advertisers also represent their product in a positive and attractive way and also give the scientific evidence to show that their product is up to date with latest technology. By using emotive and fantasy words they show that their product has maximum qualities and advantages than other beauty products.

Social Practice Analysis

This level explains the ideological customs, situations in society and provides the background knowledge of text. This study also shows the stereotypical idealized image of a beautiful woman in a society that is constructed through advertisements. According to Riji (2006) for social judgments women are treated on the basis of their physical appearance and complexion. Some people believe that these advertisements do not change their values this is somehow correct. In the olden days, women used different herbs and clay to make their skin smooth and young. Now a days there are various beauty products with the slogan that this is best and world no 1 product. Women want to look slim, fair and attractive and these products also advertised as a tool to get beauty. Advertisements mislead the women and some women believe that what is advertised is true. Advertisers control and change the mind of people and exercise their power through language.

A related study by Trampe, Stapel, Siero and Mulder (2010) show how beauty product advertisements lower female consumers' self-esteem. They assert that the advertising industry has the power to transform mundane objects into highly desirable products. Advertisers change the attitude and opinions of people and create an idealized image of beauty to influence the viewers and sell their products. Ideology of a beautiful and attractive woman is shaped through the social practice.

Conclusion

It is concluded that in advertisements various linguistic devices such as emotive words, scientific and technical words and slogans are used to attract the people. Advertisers portray a beautiful image of women that can only acquire by using their beauty products. Positive self-representation of advertisements also plays an important role to attract the viewers. Advertisers draw a problem that can only solve by using their product. Ideology of power is described through the celebrities and beauty products are advertised through the endorsement of celebrities to attract the customers. Advertisers promote an idealized beauty and shape the ideas of society and influence the consumers to purchase their product. Globalization also changes the mindset of people and now a days society focuses on the outer appearance and beauty. Advertisers use language as a powerful tool to influence their customers and manipulate the opinion of people into buying a way of life.

References

- Arens, W. F. (2002). *Contemporary Advertising* (10th Edition). New Delhi: McGraw- Hill.
Barthes, R. (1977). *Image-Music-Text*. London: Fontana.
Baudrillard, J. (2005). The finest consumer object: The body. In M. Fraser, & M. Greco (Eds.), *The Body: A Reader*, 277-282. London and New York: Routledge.

- Cook, G. (2001). *Discourse of advertising*, New York: Routledge.
- Chandler, D. (2007). *Semiotics the basics*, 2nd Edition. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Chauhan, S.G. (2006). Advertising Language: The Psychology Behind Advertising Messages. *Language in India* (Vol. 6).
- Coffin, C. (2001). Theoretical Approaches to Written Language: A TESOL Perspective. In Burns and Coffin (Eds.) (2001), pp. 93-122.
- Eagleton, T. (1991). *Ideology: An Introduction* (Vol. 9). London: Verso.
- Fairclough, N. (2001). *Language and Power* (2nd Ed). London: Routledge.
- Fairclough, N. (1989). *Language and Power*. United Kingdom: Longman.
- Fill, C. (2002). *Marketing Communications: contexts, strategies and applications*. Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
- Gramsci, A. (1971). *Prison notebooks*. New York: International Publishers.
- Hodge, R. & Kress, G. (1988). *Social Semiotics*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press. Lanteri, A., & Vromen, J. (Eds.). (2014). *The Economics of Economists: Institutional Setting, Individual Incentives and Future Prospects*. England: Cambridge University Press.
- Jhally, S. (1995). Image-based culture. Advertising and popular culture. In G. Dines, & J. M. Humez (Eds.), *Gender, race and class in media. A text-reader*, 77-88. Thousands Oak: Sage Publications.
- Kumar, P. (2004). Concept of Beauty in India: *International Journal of Cosmetic Surgery and Aesthetic Dermatology*, 4(4): 261-264.
- Lee, D. (1992). *Competing Discourses: Perspective and Ideology in Language*. London: Longman.
- Lukes, S. (Ed.). (1986). *Power*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Machin, D. (2007). *Introduction to multimodal analysis*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Machin, D. & Mayr, A. (2012). *How to do critical discourse analysis: A multimodal introduction*. London: Sage Publications.
- Mills, S. (2003). *Gender and Politeness* (Vol. 17). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Price, S. (1998). *Media Studies* (2nd Ed). England: Longman.
- Riji, H. M. (2006). Beauty or Health? A Personal View. *Malaysian Family Physician*, 1(1), 42-44.
- Trampe, D., Stapel, D. A., Siero, F. W., & Mulder, H. (2010). Beauty as a tool: The effect of model attractiveness, product relevance, and elaboration likelihood on advertising effectiveness. *Psychology & Marketing*, 27(12), 1101-1121.
- Wartenberg, Thomas E. (1990). *The Forms of Power: From Domination to Transformation*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Wrong, D. H. (1979). *Power: Its forms, bases and uses*. Oxford: Blackwell.